

A REMARK ON PERIODS OF PERIODIC SEQUENCES MODULO m

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Received: 10/12/19, Accepted: 6/13/20, Published: 6/18/20

Abstract

Let $\{G_n\}$ be a periodic sequence of integers modulo m and let $\{SG_n\}$ be the partial sum sequence defined by $SG_n := \sum_{k=0}^n G_k \pmod{m}$. We give a formula for the period of $\{SG_n\}$. We also show that for a generalized Fibonacci sequence $F(a, b)_n$ such that $F(a, b)_0 = a$ and $F(a, b)_1 = b$, we have

$$S^i F(a, b)_n = S^{i-1} F(a, b)_{n+2} - \binom{n+i}{i-2} a - \binom{n+i}{i-1} b$$

where $S^i F(a, b)_n$ is the i -th partial sum sequence successively defined by $S^i F(a, b)_n := \sum_{k=0}^n S^{i-1} F(a, b)_k$. This is a generalized version of the well-known formula

$$\sum_{k=0}^n F_k = F_{n+2} - 1$$

of the Fibonacci sequence F_n .

1. Introduction

We denote a sequence $\{a_n\}$ simply by a_n , without brackets, unless some confusion is possible. Given a sequence a_n , its partial sum sequence Sa_n is defined by

$$Sa_n := \sum_{k=0}^n a_k.$$

The Fibonacci sequence $\{F_n\}$ is defined by $F_0 = 0, F_1 = 1, F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}$ ($n \geq 2$)¹:

0, 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34, 55, 89, 144, 233, 377, 610, 987, 1597, 2584, 4181, 6765, . . .

¹Sometimes the Fibonacci sequence is defined to start at $n = 1$ instead of at $n = 0$, namely, defined by $F_1 = F_2 = 1$ and $F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}$ ($n \geq 3$), e.g., see [1, Example 4.27].

It is well-known (e.g., see [3, 6, 7, 8, 9]) that, for any integer $m \geq 2$, the Fibonacci sequence F_n modulo m is a periodic sequence. For example, for $m = 2$ and $m = 6$, the Fibonacci sequences F_n modulo 2 and 6, and the partial sum sequences SF_n modulo 2 and 6 are the following:

- $m = 2$:

$$F_n : \underbrace{011} \underbrace{011} \underbrace{011} \underbrace{011}, \dots$$

$$SF_n : \underbrace{010} \underbrace{010} \underbrace{010} \underbrace{010}, \dots$$

- $m = 6$:

$$F_n : \underbrace{011235213415055431453251} \underbrace{011235213415055431453251}, \dots$$

$$SF_n : \underbrace{012410230454432034214050} \underbrace{012410230454432034214050}, \dots$$

The periods of F_n modulo 2 and SF_n modulo 2 are the same number, 3, and also the periods of F_n modulo 6 and SF_n modulo 6 are the same number, 24. In fact, this holds for any integer $m \geq 2$, as we will see. Furthermore, if we consider $S^2F_n := S(SF_n)$ (which will be discussed in Section 4), then the period of S^2F_n is not necessarily the same as that of F_n .

Now, let us consider the following same periodic sequence G_n modulo $m = 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8$ (its period is 3):

$$G_n : \underbrace{011} \underbrace{011} \underbrace{011}, \dots$$

Then its partial sum sequence SG_n becomes as follows:

1. $m = 2$: $SG_n : \underbrace{010} \underbrace{010} \underbrace{010} \underbrace{010}, \dots$; period is $3 = 3 \times 1$
2. $m = 3$: $SG_n : \underbrace{012201120} \underbrace{012201120} \underbrace{012201120} \underbrace{012201120}, \dots$; period is $9 = 3 \times 3$.
3. $m = 4$: $SG_n : \underbrace{012230} \underbrace{012230} \underbrace{012230} \underbrace{012230}, \dots$; period is $6 = 3 \times 2$.
4. $m = 5$: $SG_n : \underbrace{012234401123340} \underbrace{012234401123340}, \dots$; period is $15 = 3 \times 5$.
5. $m = 6$: $SG_n : \underbrace{012234450} \underbrace{012234450} \underbrace{012234450}, \dots$; period is $9 = 3 \times 3$.
6. $m = 7$: $SG_n : \underbrace{012234456601123345560}, \dots$; period is $21 = 3 \times 7$.
7. $m = 8$: $SG_n : \underbrace{012234456670} \underbrace{012234456670}, \dots$; period is $12 = 3 \times 4$.

In this note, given any periodic sequence G_n modulo m (not necessarily the Fibonacci sequence modulo m), we give a formula of the period of the partial sum sequence SG_n in terms of the period of the original sequence G_n .

Theorem 1. *Let p be the period of a periodic sequence G_n modulo m . Then the period of the partial sum sequence SG_n modulo m is equal to*

$$p \times \text{ord}(SG_{p-1} \bmod m),$$

where $\text{ord}(x)$ denotes the order of an element x of \mathbb{Z}_m . In particular, if m is a prime, then the period of the partial sum sequence SG_n modulo m is equal to

$$\begin{cases} p & \text{if } SG_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{m}, \\ p \times m & \text{if } SG_{p-1} \not\equiv 0 \pmod{m}. \end{cases}$$

For example, in the above examples, $SG_2 \bmod m$ is equal to 2 for each m , and the order $\text{ord}(SG_{p-1} \bmod m)$ is as follows:

1. $m = 2$; $\text{ord}(SG_2 \bmod 2) = 1$.
2. $m = 3$; $\text{ord}(SG_2 \bmod 3) = 3$.
3. $m = 4$; $\text{ord}(SG_2 \bmod 4) = 2$.
4. $m = 5$; $\text{ord}(SG_2 \bmod 5) = 5$.
5. $m = 6$; $\text{ord}(SG_2 \bmod 6) = 3$.
6. $m = 7$; $\text{ord}(SG_2 \bmod 7) = 7$.
7. $m = 8$; $\text{ord}(SG_2 \bmod 8) = 4$.

2. General Fibonacci Sequence $F(a, b)_n$ Modulo m

In this section we observe that the Fibonacci sequence F_n modulo m and its partial sum sequence SF_n modulo m have the same period.

Definition 1. A sequence \tilde{F}_n satisfying

$$\tilde{F}_n = \tilde{F}_{n-1} + \tilde{F}_{n-2} \quad (n \geq 2)$$

is called a *general Fibonacci sequence*.

For such a general Fibonacci sequence \tilde{F}_n , $\tilde{F}_0 = a$ and $\tilde{F}_1 = b$ can be any integers. Therefore, we denote such a general Fibonacci sequence \tilde{F}_n by $F(a, b)_n$. In [4] it is denoted by $G(a, b, n)$, and the sequence $F(2, 1)_n$ is the *Lucas sequence* and is denoted by L_n .

For a positive integer $m \geq 2$, a general Fibonacci sequence modulo m is defined as follows.

Definition 2. Let $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}_m = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1\}$. The sequence \tilde{F}_n is defined by

- $\tilde{F}_0 = a, \tilde{F}_1 = b$:
- $\tilde{F}_n \equiv \tilde{F}_{n-1} + \tilde{F}_{n-2} \pmod{m}$ for all $n \geq 2$.

Such a sequence modulo m may be denoted by $F(a, b)_n \pmod{m}$, but to avoid messy notation, we use the same symbol $F(a, b)_n$. The following periodicity of a general Fibonacci sequence modulo m is well-known (e.g., see [6, 7, 8, 9].)

Theorem 2. For any integer $m \geq 2$, a general Fibonacci sequence $F(a, b)_n$ modulo m is a periodic sequence.

The period of a general Fibonacci sequence $F(a, b)_n$ modulo m shall be denoted by $\Pi(F(a, b)_n, m)$. For the Fibonacci sequence F_n modulo m , the period $\Pi(F_n, m)$ is called the *Pisano² period* of m and is denoted by $\pi(m)$. For some interesting results of the Pisano period $\pi(m)$, see, e.g., [6]. For example, one can see a list of the periods $\pi(m)$ for $2 \leq m \leq 2001$; for instance,

$$\begin{aligned} \pi(10) &= 60, \pi(25) = 100, \pi(98) = 336, \pi(250) = 1500, \pi(500) = 1500, \\ \pi(625) &= 2500, \pi(750) = 3000, \pi(987) = 32, \pi(1250) = 7500, \\ \pi(1991) &= 90, \pi(2000) = 3000, \pi(2001) = 336. \end{aligned}$$

As to relations between $\pi(m)$ and m , the following are known.

Theorem 3 (Freyd and Brown [2]). The following hold:

1. $\pi(m) \leq 6m$ with equality if and only if $m = 2 \times 5^k$ ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$).
2. For the Lucas number L_n , $\Pi(L_n, m) \leq 4m$ with equality if and only if $m = 6$.

Given a sequence a_n , the partial sum sequence b_n defined by $b_n := \sum_{k=0}^n a_k$ shall be called the *first derived sequence*, instead of “partial sum sequence”. The first derived sequence of a general Fibonacci sequence $F(a, b)_n$ shall be denoted by $SF(a, b)_n := \sum_{k=0}^n F(a, b)_k$.

Lemma 1. For a general Fibonacci sequence $F(a, b)_n$ the following holds:

$$SF(a, b)_n = F(a, b)_{n+2} - b. \tag{3}$$

Proof. We have $SF(a, b)_0 = F(a, b)_0 = F(a, b)_2 - F(a, b)_1 = F(a, b)_2 - b$. So, we suppose that $SF(a, b)_n = F(a, b)_{n+2} - b$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} SF(a, b)_{n+1} &= SF(a, b)_n + F(a, b)_{n+1} \\ &= F(a, b)_{n+2} - b + F(a, b)_{n+1} \\ &= F(a, b)_{n+2} + F(a, b)_{n+1} - b \\ &= F(a, b)_{n+3} - b \\ &= F(a, b)_{(n+1)+2} - b. \end{aligned}$$

²Pisano is another name for Fibonacci (cf. Wikipedia [10]).

□

Equation (3) is a generalized version of the following well-known formula of the Fibonacci sequence [5]:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n F_k = F_{n+2} - 1.$$

From Equation (3), we get the following

Corollary 1. *For any positive integer $m \geq 2$, a general Fibonacci sequence $F(a, b)_n$ modulo m and its first derived Fibonacci sequence $SF(a, b)_n$ modulo m have the same period:*

$$\Pi(F(a, b)_n, m) = \Pi(SF(a, b)_n, m).$$

Lemma 2. *If $\Pi(F(a, b)_n, m) = p$, then we have*

$$SF(a, b)_{p-1} = \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} F(a, b)_k \equiv 0 \pmod{m}. \tag{4}$$

Proof. There are two ways to prove this.

(I) It follows from Lemma 1 that $SF(a, b)_{p-1} = F(a, b)_{p+1} - b$. Since the period of the general Fibonacci sequence $F(a, b)_n$ modulo m is p , we have $F(a, b)_{p+1} \equiv F(a, b)_1$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} SF(a, b)_{p-1} &= F(a, b)_{p+1} - b \\ &\equiv F(a, b)_1 - b = 0 \pmod{m}. \end{aligned}$$

(II) By Corollary 1 $\Pi(SF(a, b)_n, m) = p$. Hence, $SF(a, b)_0 \equiv SF(a, b)_p$, namely,

$$F(a, b)_0 \equiv \sum_{k=0}^p F(a, b)_k = \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} F(a, b)_k + F(a, b)_p.$$

Since $F(a, b)_0 \equiv F(a, b)_p \pmod{m}$, we get

$$SF_{p-1} = \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} F(a, b)_k \equiv 0 \pmod{m}.$$

□

Indeed, in the following examples we do see the above mod formula (4).

Example 5. For the Fibonacci sequence F_n modulo m

- $m = 2$: $\pi(2) = 3$. $\underbrace{011} \underbrace{011} \underbrace{011} \underbrace{011} \dots$

- 2. $m = 3: \pi(3) = 8.$ $\underbrace{01120221}_1 \underbrace{01120221}_2 \underbrace{01120221}_3 \underbrace{01120221}_4 \dots\dots$
- 3. $m = 4: \pi(4) = 6.$ $\underbrace{011231}_1 \underbrace{011231}_2 \underbrace{011231}_3 \underbrace{011231}_4 \dots\dots$
- 4. $m = 5: \pi(5) = 20.$ $\underbrace{01123033140443202241}_1 \underbrace{01123033140443202241}_2 \dots\dots$
- 5. $m = 6: \pi(6) = 24.$ $\underbrace{011235213415055431453251}_1 \underbrace{011235213415055431453251}_2 \dots$
- 6. $m = 7: \pi(7) = 16.$ $\underbrace{0112351606654261}_1 \underbrace{0112351606654261}_2 \underbrace{0112351606654261}_3 \dots$
- 7. $m = 8: \pi(8) = 12.$ $\underbrace{011235055271}_1 \underbrace{011235055271}_2 \underbrace{011235055271}_3 \underbrace{011235055271}_4 \dots$

3. Periods of Periodic Sequences Modulo m

The first derived sequence $SF(a, b)_n$ modulo m of a general Fibonacci sequence $F(a, b)$ modulo m is periodic and has the same period as that of the general Fibonacci sequence $F(a, b)$ modulo m . As seen in the introduction, it is not the case for an arbitrary periodic sequence modulo m . So, in this section we consider periods of the first derived sequence of a periodic sequence modulo m .

Proposition 1. *Let G_n be a periodic sequence modulo m with period p . If $SG_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod m$, then for any n we have $SG_n \equiv SG_{n+p} \pmod m$.*

Proof. The period of G_n is p , thus $G_0 \equiv G_p$. Since $SG_0 = G_0$, we have $SG_0 \equiv G_p \pmod m$. Since $SG_{p-1} = \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} G_k \equiv 0 \pmod m$,

$$SG_0 \equiv SG_{p-1} + G_p = SG_p \pmod m.$$

So, suppose that for n we have $SG_n \equiv SG_{n+p}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} SG_{n+1} &\equiv SG_n + G_{n+1} \pmod m \\ &\equiv SG_{n+p} + G_{n+1+p} \pmod m \text{ (since } G_{n+1} \equiv G_{n+1+p} \pmod m) \\ &\equiv SG_{n+1+p} \pmod m. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by induction, we get the statement of the proposition. □

Here it should be noticed that from Proposition 1 one *cannot* automatically claim that the period of the first derived sequence SG_n modulo m is p ; one can claim only that the period of SG_n is a *divisor of the period of the original sequence G_n* :

$$\Pi(SG_n, m) \mid \Pi(G_n, m).$$

In fact, we can show

Theorem 4. *Let G_n be a periodic sequence modulo m with period p . If $SG_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod m$, then $\Pi(SG_n, m) = \Pi(G_n, m)$.*

Proof. Suppose that $\Pi(SG_n, m) \neq \Pi(G_n, m)$, namely $\Pi(SG_n, m)$ is a proper divisor of $p = \Pi(G_n, m)$. Let $d = \Pi(SG_n, m) < p$ and $d \mid p$. Thus, we have that for all $n \geq 0$

$$SG_n \equiv SG_{n+d} \pmod m. \tag{6}$$

We have that $SG_0 \equiv SG_d \pmod m$ implies $G_1 + \dots + G_d \equiv 0 \pmod m$, thus

$$G_1 \equiv -(G_2 + \dots + G_d) \pmod m.$$

Now, $SG_1 \equiv SG_{1+d} \pmod m$ implies $G_2 + \dots + G_d + G_{1+d} \equiv 0 \pmod m$, thus

$$G_{1+d} \equiv -(G_2 + \dots + G_d) \pmod m.$$

Therefore we get

$$G_1 \equiv G_{1+d} \pmod m.$$

Let $p = d \times p_0$. Continuing this procedure, we get the following congruences:

- $G_1 \equiv G_{1+d} \equiv G_{1+2d} \dots \equiv G_{1+(p_0-1)d} \pmod m.$
- $G_2 \equiv G_{2+d} \equiv G_{2+2d} \dots \equiv G_{2+(p_0-1)d} \pmod m.$
- $G_3 \equiv G_{3+d} \equiv G_{3+2d} \dots \equiv G_{3+(p_0-1)d} \pmod m.$
-
-
- $G_{d-1} \equiv G_{2d-1} \equiv G_{3d-1} \dots \equiv G_{p_0d-1} \pmod m.$
- $G_d \equiv G_{2d} \equiv G_{3d} \equiv \dots \equiv G_{p_0d} = G_p \pmod m.$

Since $G_0 \equiv G_p \pmod m$, the final congruences $G_d \equiv G_{2d} \equiv G_{3d} \equiv \dots \equiv G_{p_0d} = G_p \pmod m$ become

- $G_0 \equiv G_d \equiv G_{2d} \equiv G_{3d} \equiv \dots \equiv G_p \pmod m.$

Hence $\Pi(G_n, m) = d < p$, which contradicts the fact that $\Pi(G_n, m) = p$. □

As in the proof (II) of Lemma 2, if $\Pi(G_n, m) = \Pi(SG_n, m) = p$, then we have $SG_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod m$. Therefore we get the following

Corollary 2. *Let G_n be a periodic sequence modulo m with period p . Then we have $SG_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod m$ if and only if $\Pi(SG_n, m) = \Pi(G_n, m)$.*

Next, we consider the case when $SG_{p-1} \not\equiv 0 \pmod m$.

Theorem 5. *Let G_n be a periodic sequence modulo m with period p . If $SG_{p-1} \not\equiv 0 \pmod m$, then*

$$\Pi(SG_n, m) = s \times \Pi(G_n, m),$$

where s is the order of $SG_{p-1} \pmod m$ in \mathbb{Z}_m , i.e., s is the smallest non-zero integer such that

$$s \times SG_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod m.$$

Proof. First we observe that for all $i \geq 2$

$$SG_{ip-1} \equiv SG_{(i-1)p-1} + SG_{p-1} \pmod m$$

from which we obtain that for all $i \geq 1$

$$SG_{ip-1} \equiv i \times SG_{p-1} \pmod m$$

Indeed, the first p -tuple is $\{SG_0, SG_1, \dots, SG_{p-1}\}$ and the second p -tuple is $\{SG_p, SG_{p+1}, \dots, SG_{2p-1}\}$, which is, modulo m , the same as

$$\{SG_{p-1} + SG_0, SG_{p-1} + SG_1, \dots, SG_{p-1} + SG_{p-1}\}.$$

Hence, $SG_{2p-1} \equiv SG_{p-1} + SG_{p-1} \pmod m$, thus we get

$$SG_{2p-1} \equiv 2 \times SG_{p-1} \pmod m. \tag{7}$$

The third p -tuple $\{SG_{2p}, SG_{2p+1}, \dots, SG_{3p-1}\}$ is, modulo m , the same as

$$\{SG_{2p-1} + SG_0, SG_{2p-1} + SG_1, \dots, SG_{2p-1} + SG_{p-1}\}.$$

Hence, $SG_{3p-1} \equiv SG_{2p-1} + SG_{p-1}$, thus from Equation (7) we get

$$SG_{3p-1} \equiv 3 \times SG_{p-1} \pmod m.$$

Now, let us suppose that

$$SG_{jp-1} \equiv j \times SG_{p-1} \pmod m. \tag{8}$$

We see that the $(j + 1)$ -th p -tuple $\{SG_{jp}, SG_{jp+1}, \dots, SG_{(j+1)p-1}\}$ is, modulo m , the same as

$$\{SG_{jp-1} + SG_0, SG_{jp-1} + SG_1, \dots, SG_{jp-1} + SG_{p-1}\}.$$

Hence, $SG_{(j+1)p-1} \equiv SG_{jp-1} + SG_{p-1} \pmod m$, and thus from Equation (8) we get

$$SG_{(j+1)p-1} \equiv (j + 1) \times SG_{p-1} \pmod m..$$

Hence, by induction, we have that for all $i \geq 1$

$$SG_{ip-1} \equiv i \times SG_{p-1} \pmod m.$$

Since $s \times SG_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod m$, we have

$$SG_{ps-1} \equiv \sum_{k=0}^{ps-1} G_k \equiv 0 \pmod m.$$

As in the proof of Proposition 1, we see that for any n

$$SG_n \equiv SG_{n+ps} \pmod m.$$

Hence the period of SG_n is a divisor of ps . Suppose that such a divisor is a proper one, denoted by δ . Then, as in the proof of Theorem 4, we have

$$G_n \equiv G_{n+\delta} \pmod m.$$

Since the period of G_n is p , δ has to be a multiple of p , thus $\delta = \omega p$ for some non-zero integer ω . Since $\delta = \omega p$ is a proper divisor of ps , ω is a proper divisor of s , in particular $\omega < s$. Then, as in the proof (II) of Lemma 2, $SG_n \equiv GS_{n+\omega p} \pmod m$ implies that

$$GS_{\omega p-1} = \sum_{k=0}^{\omega p-1} G_k \equiv 0 \pmod m.$$

In other words

$$\omega \times SG_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod m.$$

This contradicts the fact that s is the smallest non-zero integer such that $s \times SG_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod m$. Hence the period δ of SG_n has to be exactly ps , i.e.,

$$\Pi(SG_n, m) = s \times \Pi(G_n, m).$$

□

Therefore we get the following theorem:

Theorem 6. *Let p be the period of a periodic sequence G_n modulo m . Then the period of the partial sum sequence SG_n modulo m is equal to*

$$\text{ord}(SG_{p-1} \pmod m) \times p,$$

where $\text{ord}(x)$ denotes the order of an element x of \mathbb{Z}_m .

In particular, if m is a prime, then the period of the partial sum sequence SG_n modulo m is equal to

$$\begin{cases} p & \text{if } SG_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod m, \\ m \times p & \text{if } SG_{p-1} \not\equiv 0 \pmod m. \end{cases}$$

We note that for an element $n \in \mathbb{Z}_m$, the order $\text{ord}(n)$ of the element n is given by

$$\text{ord}(n) = \frac{\text{LCM}(n, m)}{n}$$

where $\text{LCM}(n, m)$ is the least common multiple of n and m .

Example 9. Let us consider the following periodic sequence G_n in \mathbb{Z}_m with $m = 15, 30, 36$

$$G_n : \underbrace{20190823}_{20190823} \underbrace{20190823}_{20190823} \underbrace{20190823}_{20190823} \dots \dots .$$

Then $\Pi(G_n, m) = 8$ for any m and we have that $2 + 0 + 1 + 9 + 0 + 8 + 2 + 3 = 25$.

1. $\Pi(SG_n, 15) = 8 \times \frac{\text{LCM}(25, 15)}{25} = 8 \times \frac{75}{25} = 8 \times 3 = 24$.
2. $\Pi(SG_n, 30) = 8 \times \frac{\text{LCM}(25, 30)}{25} = 8 \times \frac{150}{25} = 8 \times 6 = 48$.
3. $\Pi(SG_n, 36) = 8 \times \frac{\text{LCM}(25, 36)}{25} = 8 \times \frac{25 \times 36}{25} = 8 \times 36 = 288$.

4. Higher Derived General Fibonacci Sequences $S^i F(a, b)_n$

Given a sequence A_n , for a non-negative integer i we define the i -th derived sequence inductively as follows:

$$S^i A_n := \sum_{k=0}^n S^{i-1} A_k, \quad i \geq 1$$

where $S^0 A_n := A_n$.

Thus for a general Fibonacci sequence $F(a, b)_n$, we can consider the i -th derived sequence $S^i F(a, b)_n$. By tedious computation we can show the following formulas, which are further extensions of Lemma 1.

Proposition 2. For all integers a, b and $n \geq 0$, the following formulas hold.

1. $S^2 F(a, b)_n = SF(a, b)_{n+2} - a - (n + 2)b$.
2. $S^3 F(a, b)_n = S^2 F(a, b)_{n+2} - (n + 3)a - \frac{(n + 2)(n + 3)}{2}b$.
3. $S^4 F(a, b)_n = S^3 F(a, b)_{n+2} - \frac{(n + 3)(n + 4)}{2}a - \frac{(n + 2)(n + 3)(n + 4)}{2 \times 3}b$.

These formulas are re-expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S^2 F(a, b)_n &= SF(a, b)_{n+2} - \binom{n + 2}{0}a - \binom{n + 2}{1}b \\ &= SF(a, b)_{n+2} - \binom{n + 2}{2 - 2}a - \binom{n + 2}{2 - 1}b. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} S^3F(a, b)_n &= S^2F(a, b)_{n+2} - \binom{n+3}{1}a - \binom{n+3}{2}b \\ &= S^2F(a, b)_{n+2} - \binom{n+3}{3-2}a - \binom{n+3}{3-1}b. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} S^4F(a, b)_n &= S^3F(a, b)_{n+2} - \binom{n+4}{2}a - \binom{n+4}{3}b \\ &= S^3F(a, b)_{n+2} - \binom{n+4}{4-2}a - \binom{n+4}{4-1}b. \end{aligned}$$

So, by these re-expressions, it is natural to think that the following general formula would hold and it turns out that it is the case, i.e., we have the following result.

Theorem 7. *For $i \geq 1$ we have*

$$S^iF(a, b)_n = S^{i-1}F(a, b)_{n+2} - \binom{n+i}{i-2}a - \binom{n+i}{i-1}b. \tag{10}$$

When $i = 1$ we set $\binom{n+1}{1-2} = \binom{n+1}{-1} = 0$.

Proof. The proof is by induction. Since the formula is already proved in the cases when $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ as above, we suppose that the above formula (10) holds for $i = j$:

$$S^jF(a, b)_n = S^{j-1}F(a, b)_{n+2} - \binom{n+j}{j-2}a - \binom{n+j}{j-1}b \tag{11}$$

and we show the formula for $i = j + 1$:

$$S^{j+1}F(a, b)_n = S^jF(a, b)_{n+2} - \binom{n+j+1}{j-1}a - \binom{n+j+1}{j}b. \tag{12}$$

First we have

$$\begin{aligned} &S^{j+1}F(a, b)_n \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n S^jF(a, b)_k \quad (\text{by the definition of } S^{j+1}F(a, b)_n) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n \left\{ S^{j-1}F(a, b)_{k+2} - \binom{k+j}{j-2}a - \binom{k+j}{j-1}b \right\} \quad (\text{by Equation (11)}) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n S^{j-1}F(a, b)_{k+2} - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-2}a - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-1}b \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left(\sum_{k=0}^{n+2} S^{j-1}F(a, b)_k - S^{j-1}F(a, b)_0 - S^{j-1}F(a, b)_1 \right) \\
 &\qquad\qquad\qquad - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-2} a - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-1} b \\
 &= S^jF(a, b)_{n+2} - S^{j-1}F(a, b)_0 - S^{j-1}F(a, b)_1 - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-2} a - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-1} b.
 \end{aligned}$$

Here we observe that for all $j \geq 1$ we have $S^{j-1}F(a, b)_0 = a$, which is obvious, and

$$S^{j-1}F(a, b)_1 = (j - 1)a + b. \tag{13}$$

Equation (13) can be seen by induction as follows. If $j = 1$, then $S^{j-1}F(a, b)_1 = S^0F(a, b)_1 = F(a, b)_1 = b$. So, suppose that $S^{j-1}F(a, b)_1 = (j - 1)a + b$ holds and we show that $S^jF(a, b)_1 = ja + b$. Indeed,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^jF(a, b)_1 &= S^{j-1}F(a, b)_0 + S^{j-1}F(a, b)_1 \quad (\text{by the definition of } S^jF(a, b)_1) \\
 &= a + (j - 1)a + b \quad (\text{by the above}) \\
 &= ja + b.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &S^{j+1}F(a, b)_n \\
 &= S^jF(a, b)_{n+2} - a - \{(j - 1)a + b\} - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-2} a - \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-1} b \\
 &= S^jF(a, b)_{n+2} - \left\{ j + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-2} \right\} a - \left\{ 1 + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-1} \right\} b.
 \end{aligned}$$

We want to show

$$j + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-2} = \binom{n+j+1}{j-1}, \tag{14}$$

$$1 + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-1} = \binom{n+j+1}{j}. \tag{15}$$

To show these, we recall the following formula (Pascal's Rule):

$$\binom{n-1}{k-1} + \binom{n-1}{k} = \binom{n}{k}.$$

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & j + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-2} \\
 &= \binom{j}{1} + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{j+k}{2+k} \\
 &= \underbrace{\binom{j}{1} + \binom{j}{2}} + \binom{j+1}{3} + \binom{j+2}{4} + \dots + \binom{j+n}{2+n} \\
 &= \binom{j+1}{2} + \binom{j+1}{3} + \binom{j+2}{4} + \dots + \binom{j+n}{2+n} \quad (\text{using Pascal's Rule}) \\
 &= \underbrace{\binom{j+1}{2} + \binom{j+1}{3}} + \binom{j+2}{4} + \dots + \binom{j+n}{2+n} \\
 &= \binom{j+2}{3} + \binom{j+2}{4} + \binom{j+3}{5} + \dots + \binom{j+n}{2+n} \\
 &= \dots \dots \dots \quad (\text{using Pascal's Rule step by step}) \\
 &= \binom{j+n}{1+n} + \binom{j+n}{2+n} \\
 &= \binom{j+n+1}{2+n} \quad (\text{using Pascal's Rule}) \\
 &= \binom{j+n+1}{j-1}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus we get Equation (14). Similarly, using Pascal's Rule step by step we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k+j}{j-1} &= 1 + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{j+k}{1+k} \\
 &= \binom{j}{0} + \binom{j}{1} + \binom{j+1}{2} + \binom{j+2}{3} + \dots + \binom{j+n}{1+n} \\
 &= \dots \dots \dots \\
 &= \dots \dots \dots \\
 &= \binom{j+n}{n} + \binom{j+n}{1+n} \\
 &= \binom{j+n+1}{1+n} \quad (\text{using Pascal's Rule}) \\
 &= \binom{j+n+1}{j}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus we get Equation (15).

□

Example 16. For each case of the above Example 5

1. In the case when $m = 2$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_n &: \underbrace{011}_{} \underbrace{011}_{} \underbrace{011}_{} \underbrace{011}_{} \dots\dots \\
 SF_n &: \underbrace{010}_{} \underbrace{010}_{} \underbrace{010}_{} \underbrace{010}_{} \underbrace{010}_{} \dots\dots \\
 S^2F_n &: \underbrace{011100}_{} \underbrace{011100}_{} \underbrace{011100}_{} \underbrace{011100}_{} \dots\dots \\
 S^3F_n &: \underbrace{010111101000}_{} \underbrace{010111101000}_{} \underbrace{010111101000}_{} \underbrace{010111101000}_{} \dots\dots \\
 S^4F_n &: \underbrace{011010110000}_{} \underbrace{011010110000}_{} \underbrace{011010110000}_{} \underbrace{011010110000}_{} \dots\dots
 \end{aligned}$$

2. In the case when $m = 3$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_n &: \underbrace{01120221}_{} \underbrace{01120221}_{} \underbrace{01120221}_{} \underbrace{01120221}_{} \dots\dots \\
 SF_n &: \underbrace{01211020}_{} \underbrace{01211020}_{} \underbrace{01211020}_{} \underbrace{01211020}_{} \dots\dots \\
 S^2F_n &: \underbrace{010122111212002220201100}_{} \underbrace{010122111212002220201100}_{} \dots\dots \\
 S^3F_n &: \underbrace{011210120202221022112000}_{} \underbrace{011210120202221022112000}_{} \dots\dots \\
 S^4F_n &: \underbrace{012122022110212210121111120200100221020021202222201011211002101102010000}_{} \dots\dots
 \end{aligned}$$

From Theorem 6 we get the following.

Theorem 8. We let $p_i = \Pi(S^i F(a, b)_n, m)$ with $p_0 = \Pi(F(a, b)_n, m)$. Then we have

$$\Pi(S^{i+1} F(a, b)_n, m) = \text{ord}(S^i F(a, b)_{p_i-1} \bmod m) \times \Pi(S^i F(a, b)_n, m).$$

In particular, if m is a prime, we have

$$\Pi(S^{i+1} F(a, b)_n, m) = \begin{cases} \Pi(S^i F(a, b)_n, m) & \text{if } S^i F(a, b)_{p_i-1} \equiv 0 \pmod m, \\ m \times \Pi(S^i F(a, b)_n, m) & \text{if } S^i F(a, b)_{p_i-1} \not\equiv 0 \pmod m. \end{cases}$$

Acknowledgements. The author would like to thank Kazuya Hamada for providing him a question which led to this present work, Marc Renault and Osamu Saeki for useful comments, the referee for his/her thorough reading and useful comments and suggestions, and Bruce Landman for his thorough editorial work. The author is supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Numbers JP19K03468.

References

- [1] M. Beck and R. Geoghegan, *The Art of Proof - Basic Training for Deeper Mathematics*, Undergraduate Texts in Mathematics, Springer, New York, 2010.
- [2] P. Freyd and K. S. Brown, Periods of Fibonacci sequences mod m , “E3410”, *Amer. Math. Monthly* **99** (1992), 278–79.
- [3] J. D. Fulton and W. Morris, On arithmetical functions related to the Fibonacci numbers, *Acta Arith.* **16** (1969), 105–110.
- [4] R. Knott, Generalising the Fibonacci Series, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Fibonacci/fibGen.html>
- [5] E. Lucas, *Théorie des nombres, 1*, Paris: Gauthier-Villars, 1891, available at <https://archive.org/details/thoriedesnombr01lucauft/page/n7/mode/2up>
- [6] M. Renault, The Fibonacci sequence modulo m , <http://sites.math.rutgers.edu/~zeilberg/essays683/renault.html>.
- [7] A. P. Shah, Fibonacci sequence modulo m , *Fibonacci Quart.* **6** (1968), 139–141.
- [8] A. Vince, The Fibonacci sequence modulo n , *Fibonacci Quart.* **16** (1978), 403–407.
- [9] D. D. Wall, Fibonacci series modulo m , *Amer. Math. Monthly* **67** (1960), 525–532.
- [10] Fibonacci, *Wikipedia*, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fibonacci>.